

Original Article

ASSESSMENT OF N-POWER TEACH PROGRAMME ON YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN ENUGU STATE

Ezennia Anulika Geraldine, Ukwuaba Loretta Chika PhD and Dr Adaobi Victoria Nwoye

Abstract

This study examines the extent to which N-power Programme has promoted Youth empowerment in Enugu State. The study was guided by one research question and one hypothesis. Descriptive survey research design was adopted and the population of the study was 5000 Youths who had participated in the N-Power programme in Enugu state.. A sample of 473 was drawn using the multi-stage sampling procedure drawn from two sensational zones in the state. Data collecting instrument was the researcher’s structured questionnaire which was subjected to face validation by three research experts. The overall reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research question while the t-test statistics was used to test the null hypothesis findings among others show that to a great extent, N-power Teach programme has promoted Youth empowerment. Further, the extent to which N-power building has promoted Youth Empowerment was great. Based on these findings, some recommendation among others were made which was the expression of facilitators of N-power Teach Programme to further trainings on pedagogical skills required to meet the 21st century skills.

Keyword: Assessment, N-power, Youth Empowerment.

Department of Continuing Education and Development Studies, Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Esut)

E-mail anulikaezennia@gmail.com,
chika.ukwuaba@esut.edu.ng,
Adaobi.nwoye@esut.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08037102015,
08066884633, 07036782612

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17020242>

Introduction

One of the major reasons developed nations invest substantial financial resources in human capital development, especially among the youths, is that the youth have sufficient energy, creative drives, and desire to change their world. The youth are conceived as people between 15 and 24 years old (United Nations as cited in UNESCO 2021). Thus, it could be conceived as a transition period from being dependent to a period in which the individual is independent. Although the definition of youth varies from scholar to scholar and country to country. In Nigeria, a youth is

seen as one under the age of 15 to 20 years (Nigeria National Youth Policy, 2019).

Interestingly, the global youth population in 2019 was estimated at 2,000,000,000 billion, while the sub-Saharan African youth population was 211,000.000 million (United Nations, 2019). In Nigeria, Odey and Sambe (2019) reported that the estimated youth population between 18 and 35 is 52.8 percent rate was around 53.40 percent in 2020, while the figure continued to shoot up as of January 2021 (National Bureaus Statistics, NBS, 2020).

To cushion the adverse effect of youth unemployment in the country, previous governments, both military and civilian, had adopted policy measures by introducing several youth empowerment programmes. Some of these programmes are Movement for Youth Actualization international (MYAI), Lagos digital village (LDV), International Centre for Development Affairs (ICDA), United Nations of Youth Network Nigeria (UNYNN). Foundation for skills Development (FSD), Youth for Technology Foundation (YTF), Diamond-Crest for Youth Education Foundation (DCYEF), Youth Entrepreneur Support Programme (YES-P), Graduate Internship Scheme (GIS). Others are Youth Initiative for Sustainable Agriculture in Nigeria (YISA), Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P) Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YEIN), Youth Empowering People (YEP), Young Entrepreneurs of Nigeria (YEN), Africa Youth Empowerment Nigeria (AYEN), Youth Empowerment and Development Initiative (YEDI) (Odey & Sambe, 2019) and recently, the Nigeria Power (N-power) programme established in 2016 by the prevents government.

The N-power programme is one of the National social Investment programme designed to address the problem of Youth empowerment and improve social development (Dauda et al, 2021). The programme has become a household name and plat for where most Nigerians can access skills acquisition and development. Hence, the federal government designed a job creation and empowerment initiative of the social investment programme to drastically reduce youth unemployment in Nigeria (Akujuru & Enyirko, 2019). The programme's scope spans providing young graduates and non-graduates within the age brackets of 18-35 years with the skills, tools and livelihood to enable them to advance from empowerment to entrepreneurship and innovation.

The wide coverage of the programme for graduates and non-graduates especially in the inculcation of various skills to youth within the specified age brackets conceived in the country is believed to accommodate

all categories of Youth, thereby reducing the prevalent unemployment rate. Consequently, the N-power programme is structured in six categories :{1} N-creative, {2}N-Agro,{3} N-Tech {4}N-Health {5} N-Build {6}N-Teach. However, N-Teach was designed for graduates believed to have completed their mandatory National Youth Service corps programme. The study however is focused on N-Teach, the choice of these category is premised on its widespread across a greater percentage of graduate Youth in the study area than others. Hence, the need to ascertain the extent they have promoted empowerment of Youths in the state.

While education is a key to wealth creation, Akpama and Asor (2015) asserted that it prepares people for social civil, political, and economic roles beyond the limits of elementary literacy training, which involves reading and writing, furthermore, Anjali and Smgolha, as cited in Oboqua (2021), noted that education is a panacea for social problems experienced by Youths. Thus, with the growing concern about qualified teachers in public schools, Akujuru and Enyirko (2019) reported that volunteers help implement science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) programmes in primary schools focusing on computer science, engineering, applied mathematics and other teach information knowledge (Bennel, 2017). To fill up these capes in the educational sector, the N-power Teach helps in fill this gap by improving the quality of basic education in Nigeria basic schools. N-power Teach programme aim to address youth employment by providing work skills development and improving public services in Nigeria particular by in Enugu State. However, their contributions on daily liking and Youth hardships in Enugu has yet to be discovered. Hence, there is a need for the study.

The researcher was concerned that despite government efforts to alleviate poverty by establishing various poverty alleviation programmes, such as the N-power Teach programme to improve youths living conditions, the rate to ascertain the extent to which N-power teach

programme have promoted youth empowerment in Enugu state.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study was to ascertain how N-power Teach programme has promoted youth empowerment in Enugu state. Specifically, the study sought to determine the extent to which the:

1. N-power Teach has Promoted Youth Empowerment in Enugu state.

Research Question

1. To what extent has N-power Teach promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State?

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of youths from Enugu East senatorial zone and their counterpart from Enugu West on the extent to which N-power teach has promoted youth empowerment.

Result:

Table 1 mean rating of respondents on the extent to which N-power teach has promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State = 473

S/N	N-Power teach	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Improved my reaching skills	2.82	0.81	Great extent
2	Improved my communication skills	2.63	0.84	Great extent
3	Improved my self-confidence	2.65	1.29	Great extent
4	Improved my high self-esteem skills	2.58	0.90	Great extent
5	Improved my writing skills	2.68	0.88	Great extent
6	Improved my behavior	2.78	0.91	Great extent
7	Improved knowledge in information and communication technology	2.69	0.86	Great extent
	Cluster mean	2.72	0.93	Great extent

The result presented in the table above revealed that item 1-8 had cluster mean scores of great extent shows 2.72. While the standard deviation is 0.93 which shows

Hypothesis

T-test analysis of difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which N-power teach has promoted youth empowerment in Enugu state

Method

The study was guided by one research question and one null hypothesis. The descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study population was 5000 youths who participated in the programme. Data commenting instrument was the researcher’s structured questionnaire which was face validated by three experts. The overall reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach alpha statistical tool. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation from the research question while the t-test statistic was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant findings among others show that to a great extent. N-power teach has promoted youth empowerment. The real limit of number was used as a guiding principle for decision making. This is interpreted as follows: the mean scores between 3.05 -4.00 was regarded as very great extent, 2.50-3.49 (great extent), 2.00-2.49 (low extent) and 1.00-1.99 (very low extent).

that N-power teach has greatly promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State.

Senatorial zone	No respondent	of X	SD	DF	Tcal	Pvalue	Decision
Enugu East	195	2.79	0.70	476	1.18	0.24	ns
Enugu West	283	2.71	0.64				

From table 2, show. That ($t=1.18$, $Pval = 0.24$) since the associated probability value was greater than 0.05 set as benchmark, the null hypothesis is hereby not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of youth from Enugu East Senatorial zone and those of West on the extent in which N-power teach had promoted youth empowerment.

Discussion

From findings of the research question one shows the N-power teach has greatly promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State. Respondents from both senatorial zones also affirmed this contribution following the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The similar views shared by these youths on the items clearly established the validity of N-power teach. This may also be true as study revealed the acquisition vocational skills, agricultural skills, functional literacy skills and financial skills on rural women who participated in registered community – based organization empowerment programme (Ede, 2022). By exposing these youths to the programme, they are found to improve on their teaching, reading and communication skills this invariably affords them of the opportunity to diversify their business pursuit in

References

Akpama, S.T & Andong, H.A (2016) vocational training and women empowerment opportunities in central senatorial zone. Cross River State. Nigeria National council for Adult, 16(1) 288-305.

Akujuru, C.A & Enyirko, N.C (2019). The Impact of N-power programme on poverty alleviation in Nigeria: A study of River State Global journal of political Science and Administration. 7(3) 29-50.

order to be self-reliant. It also agrees with the findings of Dauda et al (2019) that there is no significant relationship between the N-power and variables such as employment generation, poverty alleviation and skills, acquisition. In other words, the exposition of youth to N-power teach is bedeviled to contribute to their empowerment in various facets of their lives.

Conclusion

In view of the findings of this study, it was concluded that to great extent N-power teach have promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State.

Educational implications the findings have the following implications

1. Finding on N-power teach shows that it has promoted youth empowerment in Enugu State. It is possible that with the inculcation of the relevant skills on youth in any educational setting, they will be empowered and tend to be law abiding citizens.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion, the study recommend.

1. That facilitators of N-power teach should be exposed to further training on pedagogical skills required to meet with the 21st century skills.

Bennel, P (2017) Improving youth Livelihoods in sub-Saharan Africa: A review of and programmes with particular emphasis on the link between sexual behavior and economic wellbeing. Report to the interparty alleviation in Rivers State centre (IDRC)

Danda, A, Adeyeye, M.M, Yakubu, M.M, Oni D.O. & Umar. H (2019). The impact of N-power Programme on youth enterprise in Minna

- Metropolis. Nigeria Journal of Business Administration 17(182).
- Ede, C.O. (2022) Community – based organizations and empowerment of rural women in Enugu East senatorial zone. Unpublished M.ed thesis of Department of continuing education and development Studies (ESUT).
- National Bureau of Statistics (2020) Nigerian Gross Domestic product report (fourth quarter 2021) prostate.
- Nigeria National Youth Policy (2019) Enhancing youth development and participation in the context of sustainable development: https://www.evanigeria.org/national_youth_policy
- Odey, S.A. & Sambe, N. (2019). Assessment of the contribution of N-power programme to youth empowerment in Cross River State, Nigeria. International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology research 5(5), 1-3
- UNESCO (2021), by youth with youth. <https://www.emd.unesco.org>.
- United Nations {2019}
- Oboqua {2021} Influence of vocational skills programmes on empowerment of widows in Nkanu West local Government Area of Enugu State. *Journal of Environmental and Tourism Education*, 3(1) 483